

Excess water tolerance

Heritability of stem elongation ability in rice

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Inheritance of stem elongation ability in four semidwarf rice crosses was found to be controlled by two dominant genes.

Four semidwarf, nonelongating advanced lines were crossed with IR11288-B-B-69-1, which has stem elongation ability in addition to a dwarfing gene, and F₁ and F₂ seeds sown in 5 × 5-cm plastic pots. The pots were placed in galvanized iron trays in the glasshouse. At 35 d after seeding, the trays were placed in a tank and the water level raised, at 5 cm/day, to a maximum depth of 90 cm. This depth was maintained 7 d, then the tank was drained.

Stem length was measured from the root base to the uppermost node and plants categorized as elongating (stem length >20 cm) and nonelongating (stem length <20 cm).

Plants of all crosses survived a water depth of 1 m (see figure). Mean stem length of the F₁ and F₂ of all crosses was >20 cm. Most plants tended toward the elongating parents, indicating dominance of the stem elongation genotype over the nonelongating genotype.

Distributions of all F₂ populations were unimodal and continuous with single peaks. The segregation ratios of all crosses in the F₂ suggest that stem elongation ability was dominant.

Two types of segregation ratios were observed in the F₂, 13:3 for the cross BKNFR76106-16-0-1/IR11288-B-B-69-1 and 15:1 for the others (see table). Such ratios can be explained by the presence of a minimum of two genes. When the two dominant genes remain together, the typical stem elongating feature develops and plants carrying the genes resist about 1-m water depth. □

Distribution and means of parent, F₁ and F₂ plants for stem elongation ability in 4 crosses. Arrows show the mean.

Inheritance of stem elongation ability in 4 crosses. IRRI, 1987.

Cross	F ₁	F ₂ seedlings (no.)		Total	Ratio	x ²	P>
		Elongating	Nonelongating				
BKNFR76106-13-2/ IR11288-B-B-69-1	Elongating	78	6	84	15:1	0.11	0.70
BKNFR76106-16-0-1/ IR11288-B-B-69-1	Elongating	80	11	91	13:3	2.60	0.10
IR8234-OT-9-2/ IR11288-B-B-69-1	Elongating	154	16	170	15:1	2.90	0.05
IR42/IR11288-B- B-69-1	Elongating	149	7	156	15:1	0.83	0.30